

Psychological Perception of Climate Change in Pakistan

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Abstract

This research explains how Pakistanis think about climate change, how they respond to it, and what psychological factors influence their attitude and engagement in climate actions. This study is based on secondary research and the data is from existing surveys and research. It shows that although many Pakistanis are aware of climate change, only a small number see it as a top priority. Psychological distance, misconceptions, education level, and cultural norms all shape their responses in taking meaningful action for climate change. Overall, the findings show a clear gap between awareness and action, highlighting the need for clearer guidance and stronger public engagement.

Keywords: climate change, Pakistan, awareness, psychological barriers, behavior climate action.

Psychological Perception of Climate in Change Pakistan

Climate change is the long-term change in the earth's climate and weather patterns which have been observed in areas all around the world since 1800s. Although many natural phenomena such as volcanic eruptions, movement of tectonic plates and changes in earth's orbit contribute to climate change, human activities are primarily driving this change (Masson-Delmotte et al., 2021). It has been severely affecting every region around the world, causing extreme weather events like floods, droughts, heavy precipitation, extreme heat, global warming, rising sea levels and other environmental disruption. An increase in such events threatens the lives of people of the world. Pakistan, stands as the fifth most vulnerable country to climate change globally according to Global Climate Risk Index and was ranked as the most affected country in 2022 due to the devastating super floods. A developing country like Pakistan already has weak economy, agriculture and healthcare system, these natural disasters worsen country's condition and are becoming obstacle in the development. Therefore, awareness and understanding of people of Pakistan towards climate change is crucial. People tend to exhibit a mix of procrastination, denial, and a focus on immediate concerns to reduce discomfort, anxiety and stress when faced with long-term global problems like climate change. This behavior of people leads to a gap between awareness of the issue and taking action. Studies show that public perceptions strongly influence support for climate-change mitigation and adaptation measures (Bord et al., 2000). Understanding these psychological responses will help explain why only some people take measures and others do not. Additionally, differences in climate-related behavior may be shaped by social factors such as education, confidence, and generational attitudes. In Pakistan, individuals with higher access to education and information often have greater confidence in

understanding climate issues and making independent decisions, while others may rely more on traditional beliefs or immediate daily concerns. Younger students and older generations may experience cultural pressures, limited confidence, or a reliance on established norms, which can influence how seriously they perceive climate risks. Not knowing enough about how people in Pakistan think and feel about climate change makes it harder to create good policies and get the public involved. For this reason, this study asks: How do local people in Pakistan perceive climate change and what psychological factors shape this perception. This research contributes to existing knowledge by closely examining public perceptions and attitudes towards their responsibility in climate change mitigation within Pakistan.

Literature review

As climate change intensifies, many parts of the world are experiencing record heat, floods, and other extreme events. Global research shows that these disruptions have increased public concern about climate risks. For example, the People's Climate Vote 2024, the largest international survey on climate opinions, found that people across regions recognize climate change as a growing threat and believe it is already affecting their lives. These findings indicate that public perceptions play a major role in shaping climate responses. In Pakistan, much like around the world, a large majority of people are concerned about climate change. According to a World Bank report, 8 in 10 Pakistanis say they are concerned about its impacts. Although around 80% of Pakistanis express concern about climate change, this concern does not always translate into prioritizing the issue. According to the World Bank (Gallup & Gilani, 2024), fewer than 25% of respondents identify climate change as one of their "top three problems." This gap between concern and prioritization indicates that many people in Pakistan recognize climate

change as a threat but do not treat it as an immediate or personal issue. Studies in psychology and behavioral science show that people's actions toward environmental issues are strongly shaped by their attitudes, beliefs, and values (Steg & Vlek, 2009). People often view climate change as a broad societal problem rather than a personal threat. Because they cannot experience its effects directly in their daily lives, their behavioral response tends to be slow (Helgeson et al., 2012). Psychologists also describe climate change as an "evolutionary mismatch" or a kind of "evolutionary trap". Human brains are wired to react strongly to immediate, visible dangers but respond weakly to slow, abstract, and long-term threats such as climate change. This natural bias toward short-term survival makes individuals focus more on urgent daily issues than on gradual environmental risks. Research shows that people often avoid or minimize climate-change information because it triggers feelings of fear, guilt, or helplessness (Norgaard, 2011). Individuals may even recognize climate change as a serious problem but still fail to take meaningful action due to emotional coping processes and social expectations (Norgaard, 2009). Cognitive dissonance further reinforces this pattern, as people tend to downplay climate risks when such information challenges their everyday behaviors or identity (Stoknes, 2015). To understand what Pakistanis believe about the causes of climate change, a nationally representative sample of adults was asked: 'What do you think global warming is caused by the most?' In response, 29.4% said 'people's behavior,' 33% said 'natural causes,' 6.9% said 'farming,' and 14.8% said 'industries' and 15.8% said that they did not know. Studies suggest that factors such as social norms, self-efficacy, and the absence of guidance or mentorship can influence how individuals of different age groups engage in climate-change actions. This data helps explain how willing people are to support or participate in climate-change actions. Research shows that poverty and daily survival pressures also limit how actively people in

Pakistan can engage in climate-change actions, even when they are aware of the problem (World Bank, 2021). Overall, the studies show that even though many people know climate change is a serious problem, their actions depend on a lot of things, like what others around them think, how confident they feel, and whether they get proper guidance. Because of this, it becomes important to understand what people actually believe about climate change and how these beliefs shape the way they respond to it.

Methodology

This research is entirely based on information collected from existing research, reports, and surveys about climate change perceptions in Pakistan and around the world. I did not conduct my own survey or experiment. Instead, I used a secondary-research approach, which means I gathered data that has already been collected by other researchers and organizations. First, I searched for reliable sources such as academic papers, World Bank reports, Gallup Pakistan surveys, and international climate opinion studies. I selected sources that were recent, relevant to public attitudes, and provided clear data on how people think about climate change. After collecting all the data related to my research, I read and compared the findings to identify common themes, such as levels of concern, psychological barriers, and differences in awareness. Then I organized the information into different sections of the literature review: global perceptions, Pakistani perceptions, psychological explanations, and social factors. While writing, I focused on summarizing the key ideas from each source in my own words. The goal of this methodology was to understand the current knowledge on this topic and use it to support my research question about why many Pakistanis show concern for climate change but do not consider it as a serious threat and take any meaningful action.

Results

The result of this study indicates that in Pakistan although the majority of the public expresses concern with climate change, with around 80% of them worried about its impact, however fewer than 25% consider it as the country's topmost problem. This reveals a gap between awareness and action which contributes to confusion and a lack of behavioral response. Studies suggest that many individuals perceive climate change as global and future threat rather than a personal risk. These psychological factors lead people to avoid climate change information and trigger feelings of helplessness, anxiety or discomfort towards climate change action. Study reveals that there are a lot of misconceptions about the causes of climate change among Pakistanis for example survey data shows that only 28% believe its causes are linked to human behavior while some believe it is caused by natural factors and others are not sure. This reduces involvement of individuals and they feel less responsible for responding to it. The literature shows that in Pakistan other factors such as sociocultural norms and education also influence the behavior of people towards taking action, people with higher education tend to take climate change more seriously. These factors create variation in how different segments of society respond to climate issues. Overall, these findings highlight that climate change awareness exists in Pakistan but multiple psychological, cultural, and educational factors continue to limit meaningful action.

Discussion

The findings of this study reveal a gap between climate change awareness and Meaningful actions in Pakistan and this section discusses what these results mean in relation to psychological and social factors. People feel distant towards addressing climate change issues

due to psychological barriers such as lack of resources, limited awareness and understanding and feeling insignificant. This connects to the psychological explanations discussed earlier which show that people react less to problems that seem distant, abstract or not personally threatening. As a result, high awareness does not always lead to real behavioral change. There are many misconception about climate change in Pakistan which weakens motivation and results in avoidance towards climate change actions such as believing climate change impacts to be natural not inked to climate change and underestimating the link between human activity and rising global temperatures. In Pakistan, levels of education and cultural expectations also shape how seriously individuals take climate risks and this happens because people with higher education are exposed to more information about global issues. Some people often follow established norms and look into their family and community for guidance. This can make younger or less confident individuals hesitant to take independent climate related actions. One of the most important reasons people in Pakistan do not prioritize climate change action is their financial situation. Over 70% of people face financial difficulties in daily life, which keeps them focused on meeting immediate needs and makes it hard to think about long-term responsibilities. This doesn't mean people are careless; it's just that survival naturally takes priority. To make climate action more achievable, large, long-term goals could be divided into smaller, manageable steps that provide more immediate rewards. It could also help to connect climate issues to people's personal as well as professional lives, so they see why it matters and feel motivated to take action even without direct personal benefit. Because financial pressure takes up so much mental and physical energy, many people do not see climate change as something that requires their immediate attention. This is why it becomes important to communicate climate change in a way that feels personal and urgent. People need to understand that climate risks can directly affect

their own lives and the safety of their families, not just the environment in general. When individuals realize that climate change is linked to issues like health, income, and future security, they are more likely to see it as part of their personal responsibility. Encouraging people to shape their everyday life in a way that includes even small climate related actions whether at home, at school or in their professional activities could make a difference. These actions do not always have to give an immediate personal benefit but they help create a sense of shared responsibility. Making climate change feel relevant, achievable, and connected to daily life could reduce avoidance and increase engagement across different groups in Pakistan.

Conclusion

This study aimed to understand why Pakistani people, despite high awareness of climate change, show low engagement in climate related actions. Most people still see climate change as a distant or future problem, which is why they do not give it much priority in their daily life. Psychological factors like fear, confusion, and lack of understanding, along with social and cultural pressures, also make it harder for individuals to take meaningful steps. These findings mean that awareness alone is not enough. People need more clear guidance, confidence, and support so they can take small but regular actions. It is also important to make climate change feel more personal and relevant so individuals understand how it connects to their own lives. In the future, education, better communication, and simple practical steps can help reduce this awareness action gap. If people receive the right kind of information and motivation, they will be able to take responsibility and contribute toward climate change action in Pakistan.

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